

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND CULTURAL ASPECTS OF HOMELESSNESS IN MODERN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

Homelessness is a widespread problem in Kazakhstan in the conditions of liberalization of economy and market society. In the Soviet past, traditional mental values did not approve the appearance of people without a specific place of residence. Then there were almost no scientific studies on the problem of homelessness, and people had no idea about the various classifications and types of the homeless. There is a need to study the practice of Western countries in working with the homeless, since the activities of the centers of adaptation and rehabilitation of the homeless in modern Kazakhstan are mainly aimed at providing strictly defined standard services in working with such groups of people.

The purpose of the study is to describe the main characteristics of homelessness in Kazakhstan and to analyze the activities of centers for adaptation and rehabilitation of the homeless.

Included and non-included observation was used to describe the characteristics of homelessness, the activities of centers for social adaptation and rehabilitation of the homeless; The analysis of social policy of the state was carried out by means of theoretical and empirical study. The growth of new non-politicized identification groups with social, cultural, civic, religious or other new values is considered by the authors as a good ground for the development of civil society. Such a feature of modern reality is estimated as a favorable environment for the organization of volunteer activities among the population.

The program for the homeless "Housing first", implemented by many developed countries of the world, is an example of an effective solution to the problem of the homeless, however, the implementation of such a project in Kazakhstan requires a qualitatively higher level of economic and social development.

To characterize the level of protection of the homeless in Kazakhstan, the authors grouped problems of a social, economic and cultural nature. Much attention is paid to identifying the positive aspects of national culture in the social organization of society.

Among the unresolved problems in the Republic of Kazakhstan are the absence of a law on the homeless, the status of the homeless, and the lack of statistics on homelessness.

Keywords: homelessness, social adaptation, rehabilitation, social policy, civil society, individual freedom, collective consciousness.

Introduction

Liberalization of the economy, the formation of a competitive social environment, the need to improve the personal and professional qualities of a person, and to strengthen the requirements for professionalization leaves a huge number of citizens unadapted to the new conditions of the market society in Kazakhstan in a state of "isolation", "alienation", "marginalization". The reasons for non-adaptation or de-adaptation may be different: lack of initial starting capital for self-realization, psychological unpreparedness, unwillingness to work hard, addictive behavior, undesirable life circumstances, etc. The appearance of the homeless as a marginal group in the market conditions of Kazakhstan, as always, has similar reasons and prerequisites, almost the same objective and subjective circumstances. Subjective causes of homelessness are primarily related to such circumstances as divorce, quarrel, death of loved ones, mental and psychological problems, alcoholism, drug addiction, etc.

Different countries give different definitions of the homeless and calculate their number differently

(Homelessness monitoring, 2017). Some of them include in this group only those who spend the night on the street, in shelters or live in organizations for the homeless. Some consider other groups, such as women living in crisis centers or mothers' homes; migrants living in special institutions; people who are going to leave places of long-term stay (orphans, prisoners, people with mental disorders); elderly single people in veterans' homes; people who do not have rights to the housing in which they live, or who are threatened with eviction; people living in conditions of domestic violence; living in non-standard, inadequate housing, for example, in shacks; living in unsafe housing according to construction standards; living in overcrowded premises, etc. This approach gives a broader understanding of homelessness and social isolation, but also requires a lot of effort to account for all types and types of homeless people, and is very difficult.

The "Housing first" program, which is implemented in most developed countries and is an innovative form of solving the problems of the homeless, is also known among Kazakhstanis. In Kazakhstan, the

homeless are mainly provided with basic, simple services: living in shelters, providing food, clothing, medical services and other types of social support. There are too many social groups in need of housing (youth, large families, military, poor), so providing, first of all, own housing for the homeless is almost unrealistic at this stage of society's development.

Main part

Today, the basic Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan begins with Article 1, where: Kazakhstan asserts itself as a democratic, secular, legal and social state, whose highest values are the person, his life, rights and freedom (Decree of the Constitutional Council of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2003). Despite declaring itself a social state, no law defines homelessness, only in the Law "On Special Social Services" of December 29, 2008 No. 114-IV (Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2008) homelessness is defined as the basis for which a person (family) may be recognized as being in a difficult life situation. A homeless person in Kazakhstan is a person who actually does not exist, and they call him a person without a fixed place of residence (BOMZH). Since there is no law on the homeless, their legal status is not determined, they do not have registrations, and they are not even registered.

The study of homelessness within the model of the new orthodoxy allows European researchers to consider it not only as an individual problem, but also as a structural problem. According to their statement, the risk of homelessness increases significantly in the absence of the following three factors: personal opportunities, access to informal support and access to official support. At the same time, the absence of all three factors will lead to a greater risk, and each of them separately creates risky situations to a certain degree (Nicholas Pleace, 2016:21).

Power, educational resources and success give the rich security and freedom, while poverty forces them to take constant risks (George Ritzer, 2018:589). In market conditions, poor people often face the problem of homelessness. There is no doubt that the desire for forced development of Kazakhstan with the participation of only the most successful part of the population will leave the poorest groups, who have neither material nor spiritual resources, in a state of social isolation. Today, the most advanced part of society uses the positive influence of globalization for its formation and personal growth, while the unsuccessful ones become outsiders, and replenish the number of marginal layers of society, threatening the social security of the state. Another unfavorable situation for Kazakhstan is the outflow of educated youth, specialists in the development of foreign countries in search of a better life.

When there are insufficient personal resources, there is no access to informal support, social services, civil society institutes, volunteers help to deal with risks. In Kazakhstan, the dominant sector remains the state, and the pressure of society on the state to strengthen social policy is still insufficient to solve the urgent, primary problems of citizens, related to housing, proper nutrition, etc.

Interest in studying homelessness by specialists in the social sphere still leaves much to be desired. An effective solution to the problem of the homeless, the development of civic activity in society is not possible without the active participation of specialists in the social sphere, sociologists and social workers. According to Kazakh scientists, religious, ethnic, cultural, and linguistic diversity in Kazakhstan contributes to the erasure of mental boundaries in people and the formation of transnational identities (Chernykh, 2018:223-224). In the reflexivity of the modern world (George Ritzer, 2018a:584), new non-politicized identity groups with social, cultural, civic, religious or other new values are growing. This is good ground for the development of civil society. This feature of modern reality must be taken into account for the organization of volunteer activities among the population.

The difficulty of the life situations of the homeless allows us to group the existing problems in Kazakhstan into several main groups.

The first group of problems is directly related to the solution of socio-economic problems of the Kazakh society.

Liberalization of economic life should be carried out taking into account the cultural features of the country. In the post-Soviet states, there are high paternalistic expectations. Society is oriented towards the state, and depends on it to a large extent. Such dependence of society is directly related to the Soviet past, where the control of the state over social and economic processes was absolute. A direct consequence of such dependence was the lack of independence of the majority of the population, which, in turn, became the cause of high paternalistic expectations (Akimbekov, 2018:69). Currently, the state should mobilize society in the prevention of poverty, homelessness, and for this purpose effectively use the potential of the solidarity model of social protection of the population (Government Concept, 2001). There is a huge difference between the solidarity models of social protection in different countries. In Kazakhstan, the role of the state in the social protection of citizens may remain predominant, given its dominant role in public life, as well as in determining indicators of the social welfare of the population, such as the size of the subsistence minimum, the amount of wages, its minimum amount, pensions and the like.

In fact, the main source of financing and social protection of the population in Kazakhstan is the state, and the participation of business and the non-governmental sector in this process is insignificant for the effective development of civil society. The improvement of civil society is directly related to the level of economic development of the country, the nature of religious and mental values of the population, democratic changes occurring in various spheres of public life at this stage of society's development. The development of the economic system requires a high educational and cultural level of the population, a variety of interests and needs.

Practical experience of developed countries, for example, the strategic model Housing First, shows an active solution to the problem of the homeless. According to evidence, starting from the USA in the 1990s,

this model was used by several European countries, including Canada. The creation of the online library "The Homeless Hub" is one of the strengths of the Canadian Observatory on Homelessness (COH) (2019). The government of New Zealand announced a package of homeless people, including 63.4 million. New Zealand dollars (58.6 million Australian dollars) for the Housing First social program (Housing First model, 2018). As the experiences of foreign countries show, the application of the Housing First program in practice led to a significant reduction in the costs of health care, justice, and most importantly, there is a positive effect, from an economic point of view, for the successful functioning of the activities of social institutions of society.

Foreign researchers distinguish three categories of homeless: temporary, episodic and chronic (Arce, 1983). The first category of homeless people who live in hostels, centers for immigrants and refugees, in medical institutions or institutions of the penitentiary system, with relatives, friends or in their cars are called temporary (hidden) homeless people. The second category is "episodic homeless" living in permanent homeless shelters. The third is "chronic homeless", who have no refuge, except for temporary shelters, which are open during difficult weather conditions (winter, for example) (Homelessness, 2017).

So that the temporary homeless do not turn into episodic and chronic homeless, it is necessary to invest more in affordable housing. The growing number of homeless causes many problems for society, ranging from aggression to moral degradation, diseases, crimes, etc. Despite the circumstances of life, a person remains a person, and he must have his own home. No one wants to be homeless voluntarily.

The number of temporarily homeless people in Kazakhstan is much higher than episodic and chronic homeless people. These are mainly rural migrants who have moved to big cities, guest workers (foreign labor migrants), young families renting an apartment, people living in hostels, living with their relatives, etc. Still surviving traditions allow many homeless people to find temporary accommodation with their loved ones. There have been cases when families with many children find themselves on the street, in houses in a state of disrepair, unfit for housing, due to a lack of bodies, a fire or an accident. Volunteers appear who advance ideas to attract the public's attention to solving the problems of the homeless, orphans, women, etc. For example, the charity fund "Kareket" was created with the initiative of volunteers, the main goal of which is to collect money for the purchase

The second group of problems in working with the homeless is made up of cultural problems. In modern conditions, the loss of traditional values leads to the preservation of distance between generations, and as a result, aggressiveness, impatience, up to rejection of loved ones in difficult life situations become common phenomena. Among the homeless there are many people who have families, children and even grandchildren. It is impossible to deny the fact that nowadays, instead of traditional relations, there are also personal

and conscious interactions between people of different generations.

Episodic and chronic homelessness is, most likely, a new social phenomenon for the history of our state. Collective consciousness, based on traditional values, brought people together, helped to solve difficult life problems together. Despite the criticism of traditional values as archaic, which have lost their role in new social conditions, there is a need to restore those of them that play the role of social support, social protection, and also strengthen the moral positions of the individual. The priority of collective consciousness over individual is basic in Eastern culture. Passing through the individualization of values, in the conditions of the capitalization of the economy, the society already realizes the necessity of not mechanical, but organic solidarity, so to speak, according to the expression of E. Durkheim (Durkheim, 1991). It is possible to come to civil society through the individual freedom of everyone, but the use of a collective resource in the form of social capital will help unite society and act as a group subject.

The methodology of the study of social capital is based on the work of foreign scientists D. Coleman (Coleman, 1990), R. Putnam (Putnam, 1995), F. Fukuyama (2004), P. Bourdieu, defining it as a group resource, value, public good, group identity and trust (Bourdieu, 2002). Social capital is a multidimensional concept and must be conceptualized as such to have any explanatory value (Eastis, 1998:42). Scientifically, the study of the concept of the classics of postmodernist sociology contributes to the enrichment of the social and humanitarian science of Kazakhstan with new conceptual approaches, and to understand the tendency of the development of human civilization.

However, it is possible to create a national model of civil society, using the potential of collective consciousness, and go from collective consciousness to the improvement of individual consciousness. At the moment, the development of Kazakh society is going exactly along this path. The development of individual freedom does not mean its absolutization, it is also necessary to preserve the collective consciousness, as the fundamental basis of the Eastern mentality.

There is a mistaken opinion that modernization is a transition from a national model of development to a single, universal one. In practice, different regions and countries develop their own models (2017).

Question for discussion

In the book by J. Ritzer, J. Stepnitsky, three main paradigms of modern culture can be found, such as cultural differentiation, cultural convergence and cultural hybridization (Pitzer, 2018: 598-608). Each of them considers the peculiarities of the interaction of global and local culture in the conditions of globalization. It is possible to observe the presence of elements of each of them in the social reality of Kazakhstan. The paradigm of cultural differentiation (S. Huntington) advocates the preservation of the identity of each culture, cultural hybridization (R. Robertson) characterizes the emergence of some hybrid forms of global and local culture in the spirit of glocalization, cultural convergence (J. Ritzer) demonstrates the worldwide spread of such phenomena

as McDonaldization, Americanization and capitalization economy.

Preservation of national culture is one of the possible options for the formation of a civil society with the potential of spiritual values of nations. For example, the thesis that came from antiquity "antiquity in the service of modernity" is extremely popular in modern China. And this is no accident: the support of spiritual values of Chinese civilization makes it possible to carry out a flexible course of reforms, focused on social and political stability (Mansurova, 2012). Since 2017, the state program "Spiritual Revival" has been implemented in Kazakhstan. It should lead to the actualization of models based on interactions between Western and Eastern civilizations. Collective solidarity, which is the basis of the mentality of Kazakhs, has always replaced many social functions of official and public organizations in the process of social support of vulnerable groups of society. As for the individualization of consciousness, it can become the basis of the conscious unification of the population, instead of the traditional one based on stereotypes.

The culture of subordination as the main model of socialization of citizens can be traced in the organization of the centers of adaptation and rehabilitation of the homeless in Kazakhstan. Numerous observations of the activities of specialists of social services indicate the strictly normative nature of their work, and this motivates both specialists and their clients to work together. The results of the observation as a researcher of the activities of the Almaty city center of social adaptation showed that all efforts of the center's workers, specialists, including social workers, psychologists, medical workers, and lawyers, are carried out strictly according to certain "Standards".

At the time of observation in December 2017, there were 173 people in the center, of which 136 were men, 37 were women; 32 people in the dormitory. For comparison, at the time of observation in April 2017, there were 209 people in the center, of which 56 were women, 153 were men; 35 people in the overnight unit (only overnight accommodation is provided). On average, about 75% of ward centers are men. The average age is 35-55 years. The largest share of wards are Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians, about 50% of them; Kazakhs, Tatars, Uighurs, Uzbeks make up about 30%, other Caucasians, Koreans - about 20%. Also, in the statistics of the center, you can find information about how many people moved to the center of social adaptation from places of restriction of freedom. Most of the working time is spent working with documents, primarily documenting the cases of wards, in addition, compiling weekly statistical reports, cooperating with the migration police, participating in the work of the social patrol, helping wards to restore documents (obtaining a registration certificate, restoring identity documents, obtaining right to allowance). Institutional services are also provided (e.g., housing, meals, assistance in processing documents). The results of the study showed the absence of a complex methodology and technology in the activity of the Center for Social Adaptation of the Homeless, neglect of conducting trainings and discus-

sions in working with them. The center actively cooperates with non-profit organizations, including three of them that also help the homeless. The direct observation of the daily life of homeless people allowed us to conclude that the task of providing emergency support to the homeless is mainly being implemented. This is only related to the activities of one center for social adaptation and rehabilitation of the homeless. Despite the existence of state documents [20], testifying to the need to change the public consciousness of citizens in the direction of democratization, many homeless centers have not yet managed to rebuild their activities in accordance with the requirements of modern reality. As long as the subjects of social work in the form of social centers do not change their activities, using active methods and technologies, it will be impossible to adapt people who are in difficult life situations to society in a new way.

Conclusion

Today, the lawless situation of the homeless in Kazakhstan deprives them of everything, even to prove their existence. The first step for our country should begin with the development of a law on the homeless in order to determine their legal status. Further, all types of life benefits that they claim - housing, restoration of documents, provision of work, activities of social partners interested in solving their problems - all must be spelled out in the law for clarity.

The activities of adaptation and rehabilitation centers for the homeless, private charitable foundations, patrons helping homeless people cannot replace permanent, systematic, preventive work with homelessness at the state level. The absence of statistics of the homeless indicates the absence of their registration, not to mention the provision of social housing. People who ended up on the street due to an accident, objective conditions or through their own fault are perceived by society as homeless people (people without a specific place of residence), spreaders of diseases, crime or other forms of deviant behavior. In their own state, they find themselves in the position of people who are outside the law and without any rights. Complex rehabilitation and active adaptation of the homeless to society should be carried out with the joint efforts of scientists, government structures, businesses, non-governmental organizations and social services.

In Kazakhstan, there is a targeted state program "7-20-25" (Program, 2019), which offers a mortgage loan at a rate of 7% with an initial payment of 20% of the cost of housing and a loan term of 25 years. This is a preferential program for people who are in a difficult life situation. However, the lack of stable income makes such programs not very attractive for temporary homeless people.

Despite the lack of such an innovative program as Housing First in Kazakhstan, there are no less interesting social projects, for example, with the creation of crisis centers for homeless mothers (Dom Mamy, 2018). This is a charity project for women who are temporarily in difficult life situations and without housing. In the course of 18 months, such women are provided with social assistance in an atmosphere of understanding and support.

Long-term social rehabilitation of the homeless is a measure aimed at humanizing public life. When the society will understand that the homeless person is not only a person from the street, but also a family member of yesterday, who by the will of fate ended up on the street, and he does not need to be isolated, but needs to be re-adapted to society, then there will be public and personal trust.

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